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Secure and Privacy-Preserving Secondary Data Use: A Framework for Cross-Domain Computation in the Encrypted Domain

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Abstract—Secondary use of data has become increasingly relevant over the past years, referring to the repurposing of data for cross-domain applications to extract multidisciplinary insights that would otherwise remain hidden. When it comes to secondary use of sensitive data, like health data, such efforts are frequently hampered by ethical, legal, and privacy constraints. As a result, recent efforts stress the need for infrastructures that support privacy-aware data federation. Privacy Enhancing Technologies have emerged as a tool to preserve privacy throughout the entire data sharing and computation life-cycle, while ensuring adherence to regulations, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Contributing to this notion, this paper presents a privacy-aware data federation framework leveraging Fully Homomorphic Encryption to enable secure cross-domain computations in the encrypted domain, avoiding centralized data storage and ensuring Data Providers retain total control over their data. Three real-world application scenarios are investigated in this work, leveraging health data to inform insights in the education domain while performance tests showcase the viability of the approach towards lawful, privacy-aware secondary use of sensitive data.

Index Terms—secondary use of data, healthcare, privacy-preserving, fully homomorphic encryption

1. Introduction

In today’s data-driven era, vast volumes of data are generated daily across diverse sectors, including healthcare,

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education, and public administration, among others. While this growing wealth of information holds the potential to drive scientific discovery and innovation, much of it remains fragmented across geographically and institutionally dispersed repositories that, more often than not, operate in isolation [1]. Recognizing this challenge, recent efforts – including the development of common EU data spaces¹ – have sought to establish infrastructures that support secure and meaningful data sharing across domains.

To extract value from such repositories, data must not only be discoverable but also usable in ways that maintain trust among all stakeholders. Furthermore, while intra-domain analyses remain valuable, the greatest potential often lies in cross-domain or interdisciplinary correlations. Secondary use, a concept that has become increasingly relevant, refers to the repurposing of data originally collected for a specific objective. This way, multi-disciplinary data can be used to derive insights in an application domain different from the one in which data was originally generated, thus revealing patterns that would otherwise remain hidden.

However, cross-domain reuse of sensitive datasets – such as health records or learner data – ought to navigate strict regulatory and ethical boundaries. The rise of data protection regulations such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)² in Europe, Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA)³ in the U.S., and the upcoming EU AI Act⁴ have served as strong incentives for the adoption of technical solutions across industries that

1. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-spaces>

2. <https://gdpr-info.eu/>

3. <https://www.hhs.gov/hipaa/index.html>

4. [https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/regulatory-framework-](https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/regulatory-framework-ai)

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go beyond conventional data sharing models, such as centralized data aggregation or the de-identification of datasets prior to sharing.

To overcome the limitations of re-identification and exposure of sensitive data, Privacy-Enhancing Technologies (PETs) have emerged as a core enabler of secure, privacy-aware, compliant data reuse and secondary use, enabling computations and analytics to be executed over distributed datasets without compromising confidentiality or control – an essential aspect of fostering trust and participation [2]. PETs include a range of cryptographic and algorithmic methods that support data analysis without requiring exposure to the underlying information. Among these, Homomorphic Encryption (HE) [3] offers a powerful approach by allowing computations to be performed directly on encrypted data, producing encrypted results that can be decrypted only by authorized parties. This capability makes HE particularly suitable for secure secondary use in scenarios where data privacy must be strictly maintained throughout the computation life-cycle. In parallel, hardware-based solutions, such as Trusted Execution Environments (TEE), have become an integral part of the PET landscape [4] when it comes to performing privacy-preserving computations.

This paper presents an HE-powered computational framework that enables privacy-preserving, secondary use of sensitive datasets, such as health-related data, and their interdisciplinary correlation with data stemming from other domains, such as data from vulnerable populations like minors. The framework operates in adherence with legal and ethical considerations, by performing the entire computation life-cycle in the encrypted domain, across data held by independent institutions, without exposing the underlying information to the computing parties or intermediaries. Through a user-friendly interface, Data Consumers can discover available datasets, request computations based on predefined workflows, and obtain results; all while data remains encrypted and Data Providers retain full control of their data.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides an overview of the related work in the field; Section 3 presents the system’s conceptual architecture and implementation details; Section 4 explores three representative application scenarios in which data from the health domain are leveraged to inform insights in the field of education; while Section 5 discusses the performance and technical design considerations that support its applicability in privacy-preserving data integration contexts; finally, Section 6 provides the concluding remarks of this work.

2. Related Work

Within the healthcare sector, intra-domain secondary use of health data has long been recognized for its potential to enhance medical research and care delivery. Among the potential benefits lie assisting in the planning of clinical studies, assessing therapy effectiveness, and monitoring pharmaceutical safety [5]. Beyond these direct clinical applications,

secondary use has also been linked to broader improvements in healthcare quality with regard to the development of best practices aiming to process optimization and personalization of clinical decisions [6].

Initial efforts to enable cross-domain data reuse, particularly between healthcare and education, have been established as well. Early operational proofs that privacy-sensitive health records can be combined with administrative school data already exist in the UK National Health Service (NHS)⁵. The Clinical Record Interactive Search (CRIS) program [7] anonymized child and adolescent mental-health electronic health records (EHRs) for four London boroughs and then linked them to the National Pupil database and to Hospital Episode Statistics to: i) quantify inequalities in service access for “looked-after” or frequently absent children; ii) map school-level referral outliers that may signal unmet need; and iii) trace self-harm presentations across emergency departments and education outcomes.

While promising, such cross-domain efforts face ongoing technical and ethical challenges. For instance, the CRIS program encountered several limitations, such as a reliance on direct identifiers for linkage. In addition, even though linked data were anonymized, an initial exposure of identifiable information across institutional boundaries was still required. These limitations illustrate broader challenges associated with traditional data masking approaches like anonymization and pseudonymization. Research has shown that anonymized datasets can often be vulnerable to re-identification when combined with external data sources [8]. In addition, pseudonymized personal data remain classified as personal data, under the GDPR, if re-identification remains possible. While these techniques are often considered baseline or first-generation PETs [9], their limitations in high-sensitivity, cross-institution contexts have motivated the development and adoption of more advanced PETs.

Several studies across the literature have investigated the application of advanced PETs, such as Differential Privacy (DP), Secure Multi-Party Computation (SMPC), and HE, in the context of privacy-aware data federation, analysis, and processing across data ecosystems, such as data spaces, data markets, and data lakes and warehouses [10]–[18]. When it comes to HE, Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE), first proposed by Craig Gentry in 2009 [19], includes several FHE schemes that are considered the most powerful form of homomorphic cryptography as they support an unlimited number of operations and iterations, and they are gaining traction in secure data collaborations, especially in healthcare and finance.

However, FHE schemes are the most computationally intensive HE schemes while with each operation encrypted data accumulates noise, which can reduce accuracy over time. To mitigate this, advanced techniques such as bootstrapping are used to restore precision in multi-step computations [20]. In addition, it should be noted that when it comes to facilitating homomorphic encryption and decryp-

5. <https://www.nhs.uk/>

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tion in collaborative data environments, it is also important to account for suitable key management.

On another note, the use of TEEs, such as Intel’s Software Guard Extensions (SGX) [21], provides a hardware-based method for privacy-preserving computation, gaining popularity in secure cloud computing. These secure enclaves isolate sensitive data during processing, preventing exposure even in the event of a system-level breach [22].

In response to the limitations and challenges of any isolated PET approach, recent trends point toward PETs hybrid solutions, combining multiple techniques to provide stronger privacy guarantees without sacrificing data utility. Platforms like Microsoft SEAL⁶ and OpenMined’s PySyft⁷ have contributed to the development of PETs-as-a-service, making these technologies more accessible to non-experts. Despite these advances, several challenges remain. PETs like HE and SMPC still face performance and scalability issues, particularly when applied to large datasets or real-time systems. Moreover, the complexity of these technologies presents usability barriers that may hinder adoption by non-specialist practitioners.

Overall, these limitations highlight the need for PET frameworks that balance privacy-preservation with usability and can be deployed in real-world cross-domain scenarios, eliminating privacy concerns, fostering regulatory compliance, and enabling wide-spread adoption without specialized technical knowledge – a three-fold aim this work seeks to support.

3. Privacy-Preserving Framework for Secondary Use of Data

3.1. Overview

The proposed framework enables privacy-preserving secondary use of sensitive datasets through an HE-powered computational framework. It is designed for practical deployments where data is held by distinct institutions, such as clinics, research centers, or public bodies, and must be processed collaboratively without sharing the underlying plain text data. It has been implemented with a core focus on avoiding centralized data storage, protecting data-in-use, and enabling cross-domain insights from sensitive health-related data, such as using health-related indicators to support educational planning or student wellbeing, without compromising privacy. The solution considers three roles:

- **Trusted Mediator:** A Platform that provides the central user interface, facilitates cryptographic operations and secure key generation and management, and performs the decryption of the final computation result inside a TEE;
- **Data Providers:** Institutions that hold sensitive datasets and register only the description of these datasets as part of the distributed data sources of the

Trusted Mediator. Data providers retain total control over how their data may be used, including which computations are allowed while the encryption process happens at their premises;

- **Data Consumers:** Authorized entities who select datasets and computations through the central user interface. Encrypted operations are performed locally at their premises where encrypted data from data providers are transferred, without ever accessing unencrypted raw data;

Furthermore, the threat model assumes all parties are semi-honest:

- **Data Consumers** are curious but follow the protocol. They don’t have access to raw data or decryption capabilities.
- **Trusted Mediator** is trusted only insofar as its secure enclave cannot be externally inspected or tampered; therefore, neither raw nor encrypted data are transferred to the main Platform where decryption keys are stored.
- **Data Providers** are assumed to maintain the security of their local infrastructure.

3.2. Implementation Details

In this work, multiple Data Providers encrypt their data locally at their premises before they are fused and analyzed. Since only data encrypted with the same homomorphic encryption key can be jointly processed, all providers must use the same (public) key for encryption. For this purpose, asymmetric cryptographic mechanisms are considered in this implementation, as symmetric encryption would mean all providers would also hold the same decryption (private) key, making it possible for one provider to decrypt another’s data. On the contrary, asymmetric encryption allows everyone to use the same public key to encrypt, while the decryption private key remains known only to the core platform of the Trusted Mediator, where keys are generated. In light of this, the use of a TEE becomes essential, for the secure generation and management of decryption (private) keys. In addition, there was a need of selecting a suitable homomorphic encryption option that supports public keys.

3.2.1. Key Management and Secure Decryption. To ensure that sensitive cryptographic material remains protected throughout the encrypted computation process, the key generation and decryption operations in this work are confined to a TEE as they mean dealing with private keys. Specifically, Intel’s Software Guard Extensions (SGX)⁸ technology has been adopted, which creates a secure enclave, isolated from the rest of the system including the operating system and other applications. Within this enclave, the public and private keys are generated. The public key is then stored within the storage of the core platform while the decryption

6. <https://github.com/microsoft/SEAL>

7. <https://github.com/OpenMined/PySyft>

8. <https://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/architecture-and-technology/software-guard-extensions-processors.html>

key remains within and never leaves the enclave. This provides a strong layer of protection against unauthorized access or memory-based attacks, and enables the secure execution of the final decryption step inside the TEE after computations have been completed over encrypted data. By leveraging the computational capabilities and memory isolation features of SGX, a balance is achieved between performance and trust, making the integration of FHE more practical in real-world, cross-institutional data collaborations.

3.2.2. Encryption Scheme and Privacy-Preserving Computation Design. In this work, TFHE-rs⁹, a Rust implementation of Fast Fully Homomorphic Encryption over the Torus (TFHE), has been employed as a suitable HE option that supports asymmetric cryptography through public key encryption. TFHE-rs implements a variant of FHE, particularly well-suited to logic-based operations like searches and comparisons, allowing joint computations over encrypted records originating from different institutions. This makes TFHE-rs particularly effective in privacy-sensitive, cross-institutional use cases like those presented in the three scenarios that follow, which include indirect exposure tracing, time-based record correlation, and cross-domain indicator analysis, all conducted entirely within the encrypted domain.

3.3. High-level System Architecture and User Support

To illustrate the overall design, Figure 1 presents the system’s high-level architecture. It depicts the interaction between the three core roles, i.e., Trusted Mediator, Data Providers, and Data Consumers, as well as the data, metadata, and container flows across institutional boundaries. The Trusted Mediator hosts the central user interface and platform services in order to serve users with varying technical expertise, including: i) a cryptographic engine which contains the secure enclave (TEE), within which the key generator resides and it’s the place where the private key is stored and the decryption of the final computation result takes place; and a storage service, where the container repository and distribution service are placed – for encryption and computation modules, supporting a range of HE-compatible operations - and where public encryption keys are stored alongside the dataset descriptions. In addition, the high-level architecture encapsulates governance and compliance mechanisms, such as data usage agreements, GDPR compliance checks, and Data Protection Impact Assessments, which are abstractly represented, as their implementation has been described in previous work [23] and lies outside the scope of this paper.

Data Providers and Data Consumers both interact through the shared central user interface. Providers register high-level metadata, i.e., dataset descriptions – such as dataset size, number of records, schema fields, indexing

Figure 1. Architecture

information, and the dataset’s access endpoint, while Consumers browse this metadata to select datasets and computations. Providers download encryption containers from the Trusted Mediator and specify where they are deployed.

When a Consumer submits a computation request involving a Provider’s dataset, the data is encrypted locally at the Provider’s premises fostered by the provided containerized services and the public keys issued and provided by the Trusted Mediator. Consumers, likewise, download computation containers, which include pre-integrated HE-compatible algorithms, and specify their deployment endpoint. As a result, encrypted computations are locally executed at the Consumers’ premises via the containerized services. The encrypted output of the HE-compatible operation is sent to the Trusted Mediator, decrypted within the secure enclave using the decryption key that is securely stored there, and returned to the Consumer through a secure channel.

To complement the architectural view, Figure 2 presents a workflow diagram capturing the sequence of interactions from the Data Consumer’s perspective. At no point during the flow is raw data exposed to other parties, ensuring strong end-to-end privacy guarantees while enabling meaningful cross-domain analysis.

4. Privacy-aware Cross-domain Application Scenarios

In this section, three representative scenarios are presented, in which encrypted computations are performed across datasets held by separate institutions. In all cases, the original data were collected for independent purposes, and the goal is to derive new insights by securely combining and analyzing the encrypted datasets without exposing sensitive

9. <https://docs.zama.ai/tfhe-rs>

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Figure 2. Sequence

information. Each of these use cases demonstrates how health-related data can be securely repurposed for secondary objectives, such as informing education-related insights for informing interventions or decision-making (e.g., for student wellbeing, risk identification or early warning systems especially in pandemics), without violating confidentiality constraints or requiring decryption by the Data Consumer.

4.1. Scenario I

Overview: The first application scenario refers to “Identifying potential exposure clusters across institutional

records using hospital-reported infection data”. In this scenario, a public authority seeks to understand whether reported infections within one institutional setting, e.g., a hospital, correlate with attendance records maintained by another, e.g., a school or university. For example, given a set of confirmed infection dates and locations, a contact-tracing computation is homomorphically executed to identify individuals who may have been directly or indirectly exposed based on overlapping presence data.

This is implemented in this scenario as a transitive closure search, as presented in Table 1, enabling the identification of indirect chains of potential exposure while preserving the privacy of all individuals involved. The result, decrypted only by the Trusted Mediator, consists solely of a numerical count (e.g., how many indirect contacts were found), ensuring that no personally identifiable information is revealed at any point.

Repurposing health data in this way allows educational authorities to take proactive measures (e.g., classroom-level risk assessments, temporary modifications to attendance-related policies such as adjusting absence thresholds or deferring punitive or academic consequences, since attendance data often informs decisions about grading, promotion, truancy interventions, access to learning support services etc.) – all without compromising privacy or requiring access to raw health records.

TABLE 1. ENCRYPTED TRANSITIVE CLOSURE OPERATION

Field	Description
Operation Type	Transitive Closure
HE Scheme	TFHE-rs
Input	Positive Case ID, Contact ID
Result	List of contact IDs transitively connected to each positive case ID

Execution:For this algorithm, `encrypted_data` is a matrix of dimension $n \times 2$, containing the encrypted values of “Positive Case ID” and “Contact ID”. The steps are as follows:

- 1) Initialize a result matrix of dimension $n \times 2$.
- 2) Iterate over each element i in `encrypted_data`. For each sample, compare the second column (i.e., the Contact ID) of the current row with the first column (i.e., the Positive Case ID) of all other samples. If a match is found — that is, the Contact ID of the current row equals the Positive Case ID of another row — then append to the result matrix the second column (Contact ID) of the matching row.

4.2. Scenario II

Overview: The second application scenario is related to “Linking temporal patterns of confirmed health events with records of attendance or presence in a shared physical environment, to infer indirect transmission chains”. This scenario aims to examine potential correlations between

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confirmed health events and institutional patterns over time, such as student absences in an educational setting, without revealing any individual-level identifiers. This is a particularly valuable scenario in educational contexts where unexplained spikes or student absences may reflect underlying health trends that may otherwise be difficult to detect in isolation. In allowing secure correlation of health events with attendance records of educational institutions (but also and especially at district and national levels) can gain timely and privacy-preserving insight into whether absence trends are related to confirmed illnesses or broader community health (or indeed, entirely unrelated to health aspect) concerns. This allows for more informed decisions around allocating resources, early interventions, adjustments to in-person instruction (or providing multi-modal alternative student support, etc.). Such analyses being conducted without revealing or posing any risks to data privacy to pupils is critical in building trust and optimizing on the opportunities from cross-domain data use.

In this scenario, as showcased in Table 2, the framework performs a temporal correlation by comparing time-stamped encrypted health records with external activity logs encrypted separately. To support operations that involve linking records across datasets, such as join-like computations, and further reduce computational overhead, the framework includes an optional feature that allows data providers to apply non-reversible cryptographic hash function, such as SHA-256, to record identifiers before encryption. This step is performed locally at the provider’s side and is used solely for enabling index matching between datasets. It assumes that the datasets involved use a shared, consistent identifier scheme, such as a standardized, institutionally recognized key, for the same individuals across sources. By doing so, the system avoids the high computational cost of comparing homomorphically encrypted identifiers directly (computational overhead is reduced by two orders of magnitude), while ensuring that the linking process remains secure and the actual identifiers are never exposed. The correlation between records still takes place entirely within the encrypted domain, preserving privacy without sacrificing performance.

TABLE 2. ENCRYPTED CORRELATION OF HOSPITALIZATION AND SCHOOL ATTENDANCE

Operation Type	Correlation of hospitalization details and school attendance
HE Scheme	TFHE-rs
Input	<p>Health data identifier: hash ciphertext: day_entry, month_entry, year_entry</p> <p>Education identifier: hash ciphertext: attendance</p> <p>Consumer: dd, mm, yyyy (date)</p>
Result	The “attendance” of students who entered the hospital on day “dd/mm/yyyy”.

Execution: For this algorithm, `encrypted_data` is a vector containing two matrices of dimensions $n \times 3$ and $n \times 1$. The first matrix corresponds to *Healthcare* and includes the encrypted values of `day_entry`, `month_entry`, and

`year_entry`. The second matrix corresponds to *Education* and contains the encrypted values of attendance. The execution proceeds as follows:

- 1) Iterate over each identifier hash of healthcare i , for all $i \in \{0, \dots, n-1\}$, and iterate over the identifiers of education j , for all $j \in \{0, \dots, n-1\}$, until the matching identifier is found. That is, for each i , find the corresponding j .
- 2) For those matching identifiers, check whether the values `day_entry`, `month_entry`, and `year_entry` at position i are equal to the target values `dd`, `mm`, and `yyyy`. If the date matches, set `result[i] = [attendance[j]]`; otherwise, set `result[i] = [0]`. The final result is a matrix of dimensions $1 \times n$.

4.3. Scenario III

Overview: The third application scenario pertains to “*Correlating anonymized indicators of mental health with attainment outcomes across co-registered datasets*”. In this final scenario, encrypted health metrics such as indicators of mental health are analyzed in conjunction with anonymized records representing attainment outcomes in an educational setting. The goal is to explore statistical correlations between behavioral indicators and real-world results without revealing individual identities or raw data values. This scenario is particularly relevant in educational contexts where understanding the relationship between student mental health and well-being and academic performance indicators is important for designing inclusive support strategies and positive learning environments. Conducting correlations between such indicators, for instance, schools and education authorities can better assess the effectiveness of well-being programs, tailor interventions for at-risk learners or monitor long-term trends without accessing sensitive personal data. Relatedly, the CRIS program in the UK, mentioned earlier, demonstrated the real-world value of such cross-domain insights by linking mental health records with national pupil datasets relating to academic performance to explore inequalities in access to relevant services and support.

In this scenario, as presented in Table 3, the framework executes linear regression and correlation operations directly on encrypted datasets received from different Data Providers, avoiding a reliance on identifiable data for linkage, compared to the CRIS program.

Execution: For this algorithm, `encrypted_data` is a vector containing two matrices of dimension $n \times 1$. The first matrix corresponds to “Healthcare” and contains the encrypted values of `mental_illness`. The second matrix corresponds to “Education” and contains the encrypted values of `maths_results`. The steps are as follows:

- 1) Iterate over each identifier hash of health i , for all $i \in \{0, \dots, n-1\}$, and iterate over the identifiers of education j , for all $j \in \{0, \dots, n-1\}$, until

TABLE 3. CORRELATION OF MENTAL ILLNESS AND SCHOOL RESULTS

Operation Type	Correlation of mental illness details and school results
HE Scheme	TFHE-rs
Input	<p>Health data identifier: hash ciphertext: mental_illness</p> <p>Education identifier: hash ciphertext: maths_results</p> <p>Consumer: illness (The consumer chooses whether to obtain information from those who suffer from a mental illness ($illness=1$) or from those who do not ($illness=0$))</p>
Result	The maths_results of students who suffer ($illness=1$) or not ($illness=0$) from a mental illness.

finding the identifier that matches. That is, for each i , find the corresponding j .

- For those cases, check whether the `mental_illness` corresponding to that identifier equals the illness provided by the consumer. Multiply `maths_results` by the result of the comparison. If the mental illness matches, then $result[i] = maths_results[j]$; otherwise, $result[i] = 0$. The final result is a vector of dimension n .

5. Discussion

These scenarios demonstrate the framework’s ability to support diverse and meaningful secondary uses of encrypted data, without compromising the confidentiality of the underlying datasets. By enabling computations such as contact inference, temporal correlation, and regression across datasets from multiple institutions, the architecture facilitates lightweight privacy-preserving computations that would otherwise require risky or non-compliant data sharing practices.

All HE-compatible operations are executed without access to plaintext values, and optional indexing mechanisms, such as hashed identifiers, are used only when required to mitigate the computational cost of HE operations.

As reference, some performance tests have been carried out considering 100 inputs datasets. The environment main features are: Dell Precision 3560, CPU 11th Gen Intel® Core™ i7-1165G7 @ 2.80GHz × 8, 16 GB of RAM and 512 GB disk, Ubuntu 22.04.3. The performance of the HE operations for the three identified scenarios is gathered in Table 4.

TABLE 4. ENCRYPTED PROCESSING TIMES ACROSS SCENARIOS

Scenarios	Encryption	Confidential Computation	Decryption
I	3 min 36 sec	3 min 2 sec	34 sec
II	2 min 39 sec	19 sec	1 sec
III	2 min 2 sec	22 sec	1 sec

As it can be observed, Scenario I required the most time overall, taking more than six minutes for the entire computation life-cycle, including encryption, computation, and

decryption. This is to be expected given the nature of the transitive closure operation it facilitates, which involves comparing record pairs in an iterative manner to identify chains of indirect contact – an inherently more demanding process in terms of computational steps. Furthermore, all three scenarios include a non-negligible step for the encryption process, as this is when homomorphic transformation of data takes place. Even though the encryption time across these scenarios is not prohibitively expensive, it’s important to note that these tests were performed on relatively small datasets (100 inputs), therefore processing time may increase with dataset size.

Considering computational features, the tests were performed on a computer that reflects a mid-range workstation. While this setup is not excessive, it does show that the framework requires a certain level of computational capacity, suggesting that it can be used in institutional environments with at least moderated resources.

6. Conclusion

This work presented a privacy-aware data federation framework to enable secondary use of sensitive data across domain and institutional boundaries. The suggested framework facilitates encrypted computation without exposing raw data or necessitating centralized data storage by leveraging FHE. TFHE-rs, asymmetric key encryption, and secure key management inside a TEE enable multiple data providers to contribute encrypted datasets and participate in collaborative computations to support meaningful insights; all the while fully adhering to privacy and confidentiality requirements.

The three application scenarios that were presented in this paper demonstrate how the proposed architecture can facilitate cross-domain, lightweight computations that are conducted entirely within the encrypted domain, including cross-domain indicator analysis, time-based record correlation, and indirect exposure tracing. Performance testing has proved the viability of the approach using a moderately powerful computing infrastructure.

However, some limitations remain, providing avenues for future exploration. For instance, the framework assumes consistent data schemas across Data Providers, which may not always be the case in real world scenarios. Thereby, future work should concentrate on expanding the framework to facilitate interoperability with broader data governance mechanisms. Furthermore, even though the application scenarios make use of representative datasets, these remain relatively small. To confirm performance and usability at scale, additional optimization is necessary to account for larger inputs or more intricate computations, both in terms of computational efficiency and encryption overhead.

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